

MIMO Signals Processing Utilizing Optical Crossbar Linear Operator

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Abstract—This paper introduces an innovative photonic MIMO processing architecture through the adaptation of a crossbar linear operator. The merits of this approach, such as restorable fidelity and reduced programming complexity, are highlighted. Experimental validation is conducted using a 4×4 crossbar-integrated photonic chip, resulting in the reporting of an 8.4 dB power tunability and a complete pi-phase shift for every node, validating in this way the tunable weight matrix implementation. Furthermore, the paper outlines the potential directions for further enhanced performance.

Index Terms—MIMO, microwave photonics, coherent processing, wireless communications, photonic crossbar.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of enhancing spectral efficiency and data rates, multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) systems have emerged as integral components of communication standards [1], [2]. Presently, MIMO systems predominantly operate within sub-6 GHz frequency bands, characterized by limited channel bandwidth, allowing for the implementation of MIMO signal processing in the digital domain. Nevertheless, this digital processing becomes increasingly computationally intensive as the number of inputs and outputs grows, particularly in the context of massive-MIMO systems [3], [4]. Moreover, the future expansion of network capacity necessitates the exploitation of millimeter-wave bands, which provide significantly larger available bandwidth. This, in turn, requires the use of high-bandwidth Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs), known for their inherent design complexity and increased power consumption [5], [6].

Linear MIMO pre/post-processing algorithms can be conceived as a matrix-vector multiplication, with the matrix derived from MIMO channel information and serving as a set of weights applied to the transmitted or received signal vectors [7]. This multiplication can be executed using photonic linear operators, harnessing the benefits of photonics, which include increased bandwidth, reduced power consumption, and minimized latency. Such an optical MIMO processor was introduced in [8], leveraging a coherent photonic processor based on Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). Nevertheless, the SVD-based processor cannot directly enact arbitrary matrices; instead, it necessitates a digital factorization of the matrix into three constituent matrices [8]. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that the performance of

an SVD-based photonic processor is significantly affected by the presence of physical impairments, resulting in amplitude and phase errors that impose constraints on its scalable and feasible implementation, [9].

In this work, we propose the utilization of the recently introduced crossbar (Xbar) coherent linear operator architecture [9], for MIMO signal processing. This choice is grounded in its inherent capacity to directly execute operations involving arbitrary real- and/or complex-valued matrices. Notably, the Xbar architecture offers several distinct advantages over SVD-based methods: i) Efficient Programming: Unlike SVD-based approaches, which typically require at least $O(N)$ steps for programming, the non-cascading nature of the Xbar allows for programming in $O(1)$ steps. ii) Simplified Amplitude Balancing: The Xbar architecture enables a straightforward amplitude balancing scheme [10]. iii) Reduced Sensitivity to Phase Errors: It exhibits lower sensitivity to phase errors, surpassing the performance of SVD-based solutions. These advantages facilitate the creation of high-fidelity, fully reconfigurable weighting matrices. The capability of realizing any arbitrary matrix is experimentally validated using a 4×4 photonic processor implementation.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 illustrates the linear optical MIMO processing architecture, in which signal processing is executed by employing a photonic Xbar linear operator.

Fig. 1. Photonic assisted MIMO processor

The system comprises a continuous wave (CW) laser source, which is then followed by a 1:N optical splitter. This

splitter feeds N electro-optical modulators (EOMs), where each optical stream is modulated by a radio-frequency (RF) input signal. The outputs from the EOMs undergo optical filtration through a single sideband carrier suppression (SSBCS) filter, which is instrumental in preserving the phase information. The utilization of the SSBCS filter and carrier re-insertion stage is essential for maintaining phase information during electro-optical conversion, typically executed by a photodiode employing the square-law of the photodetection process, as detailed in [11]. These filtered signals are subsequently directed to the corresponding waveguide rows within the photonic Xbar processor. Each of these rows features an optical coupling stage facilitated by directional couplers (DCs) denoted as $\xi_i^2:t_i^2$, enabling the distribution of part of the modulated optical signal into the respective column, while the remainder continues to the next column. In this way, each optical signal is subdivided into M intra-column optical signals. Each of the intra-column optical signals proceeds to its corresponding Xbar node, which consists of an amplitude modulator (AM) imprinting the absolute value $w_{n,m}$ and a phase modulator (PM) responsible for imprinting the phase $\varphi_{n,m}$. Upon exiting the Xbar node the intra-column optical signals are forced to recombine in an $N:1$ recombination stage comprising a binary tree of optical Multi-Mode Interferometer (MMI) or directional couplers. The outputs of the Xbar are combined with the initial carrier and converted to mm-wave signals. The signal at each of the M outputs of the processing chip can be expressed as:

$$E_{out,m} = p_m \left(\sum_{n=1}^N w_{n,m} e^{j\varphi_{n,m}} \right) E_{in} \quad (1)$$

Here, the term p_m encompasses the transmission factors associated with losses incurred by the passive and active components, as well as the splitting ratios of the couplers used.

The proposed system architecture directly associates each matrix element with the amplitude and phase modulators of the corresponding Xbar node. This direct mapping enables the efficient implementation of any arbitrary weight matrix. Moreover, it can be programmed efficiently in a single step by configuring the amplitude and phase values through the Digital-to-Analog Converters (DACs). The rate at which the DACs operate depends on the rate at which the weighting matrix needs to be readjusted.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Fig. 2 illustrates the experimental setup employed for characterizing the 4×4 fabricated Xbar photonic chip fabricated within imec's ISSIPP50G platform [12]. The 4×4 crossbar consists of 16 computational nodes, with amplitude modulation implemented through SiGe electro-absorption modulators (EAM) and phase modulation achieved by utilizing thermo-optical (TO) effects [13]. The photonic chip is attached to a printed circuit board (PCB) which is connected externally to a DAC, which is responsible for controlling the matrix weights of the crossbar.

To assess the chip's capacity for implementing any matrix weight, the performance of the amplitude and phase modulators was thoroughly evaluated. The optical measurements are performed with a CW optical signal, generated by a tunable laser, with a selected wavelength of 1563 nm, matching the optimal response of the stand-alone EAMs. The optical outputs are captured by an optical power meter (OPM) connected to the optical fibers coupled to the chip. The system was calibrated and a coupling loss of 8dB was identified.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for 4×4 fabricated Xbar photonic chip including a microscope photo of the chip

To characterize the phase modulators for each Xbar node, the output optical power was measured at all outputs while independently adjusting the voltage applied to the phase modulators. The voltage range corresponded to an applied electrical power of 0 to 25 mW. The results, as depicted in Fig. 3, demonstrate that most phase shifters exhibit pi-phase shifts, which are essential for representing any weights. However, it can be noticed that the phase modulators in row 4 deviate from this behavior, likely due to deteriorated electrical connections on the chip.

Fig. 3. Measured transmission function versus variation of the applied to PM electrical power for.

The dynamic range of the amplitude modulators was assessed using a standalone EAM fabricated on the same chip. Fig. 4 illustrates the measured optical power at the output of an EAM implemented in the photonic chip as a function of the biasing voltage, revealing an 8.4 dB power

range. The rest of the implemented EAMs have similar behavior.

Fig. 4. Measured transmission as a function of the applied electrical voltage to EAM.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we introduced a novel MIMO processing unit based on the Xbar-based photonic architecture. We emphasized the superior capabilities of Xbar-based processing compared to the recently proposed SVD-based architecture. Experimental characterization of the 4×4 Xbar implementation demonstrated full-range phase tuning (pi-shift) per phase shifter and reasonable amplitude tuning with an 8.4 dB dynamic range, validating its capabilities to implement dynamic weightings.

The performance of the proposed Xbar MIMO processor can be further enhanced by replacing the EAMs with AMs supporting a larger extinction ratio, such as Mach-Zehnder Modulators (MZM), which offer a dynamic range of up to 20-30 dB, [14]. Additionally, implementing the proposed architecture with electro-optical or piezo-electric phase modulators, known for their greater tuning range, reduced coupling, and lower power consumption, would further enhance the performance characteristics of the proposed architecture.

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